

Workshop on data management and data deposition for biological images

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Summary

This workshop (organized on 23/06/2022) highlighted current challenges of data management and deposition in the bioimaging community in Flanders. In addition, we raised awareness about existing initiatives and solutions for data management, deposition and infrastructures available to the Flemish researcher or Core facilities. We discussed how to improve good practices for data deposition and management in bioimaging.

Introduction

This workshop was co-organized by T. Woller (VIB Bioimaging core, VIB Bioinformatics core), S. Munck (VIB Bioimaging core) and A. Botzki (VIB Bioinformatics core). The workshop was moderated by A. Botzki. Due to the complex landscape within Flanders, the organizers invited stakeholders involved in Bioimaging (FBI), high performance computing (VSC) and research data management (ELIXIR-Belgium). Flanders BioImaging (FBI) is an interuniversity consortium dedicated to biomedical imaging and advanced light microscopy, whose aim is to offer available imaging infrastructure in Flanders (<https://www.flandersbioimaging.org/>). The Flemish Supercomputer Center is Flanders' integrated high-performance research computing environment, offering services to researchers, government, and industry (<https://www.vscentrum.be/home>). ELIXIR Belgium is the national node of ELIXIR, an intergovernmental organisation that brings together life science resources from across Europe, supporting life science research and its applications in medicine and industry (<https://www.elixir-belgium.org/>).

VSC capabilities by J. Ooghe and J. Scheepers

The Flemish Supercomputer Center (VSC) is funded by the research foundation - Flanders (FWO) and is a partnership between the five Flemish universities and their university associations. High Performance Computing infrastructure at VSC can be divided in Tier-2 and Tier-1 at university and regional level, respectively. Next to supercomputing service, Tier-1 also offers data management, storage capacity, cloud platform and free trainings for both Tier-1 and Tier-2 users (<https://www.vscentrum.be/vsctraining>). The access to Tier-1 Compute and Cloud are project based, while the access to Tier-1 Data is still in development. Batch and interactive sessions are both available for Tier-1 and Tier-2 compute. Software can be installed as singularity containers, modules or user-based software. Tier-1 Data is a research data repository with data management features based

on iRODS and that uses Globus online for data sharing (<https://irods.org/>, <https://www.globus.org/>). iRODS facilitates data discovery, secure collaboration, automation based on rule engines to enforce data policies and unified storage namespaces. In addition, iRODS can serve as a platform to design deposition pipelines (<https://bmcbioinformatics.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12859-018-2576-5>). Currently, 28 PB of Tier-1 Data storage are available for active data.

So far, Tier-1 Data is not intended for long-term storage. As a result, data would be transferred after publication to dedicated repositories for archival (i.e. RDR for KUL, bioimage archive for bioimage). VSC will work on tools and integration to facilitate the transfer to those repositories. Initially the integration with the KU Leuven RDR repository based on Dataverse will be implemented and in a second phase tools for publishing in other commonly used repositories (e.g. Bioimage Archive) will be explored and if viable implemented.

FAIR data in bioimaging by T. Woller

Data and plastic waste share many similarities such as their uncontrolled proliferation and their requirement for curation. ELIXIR has developed RDMkit, which serves as a guide for data management and emphasizes every step of the data life cycle (<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org>). Recently, a study investigates the status of research data management (RDM) and analysis within the bioimaging community (<https://fl1000research.com/articles/11-638>). This study underlines the lack of RDM literacy within the bioimaging community, a pattern we also observed at FBI. Nevertheless, the RDM literacy is increasing due to trainings and the incorporation of topics related to RDM in university curricula. Despite its rising importance, the acronym FAIR and its implications are not fully understood to researchers within the bioimaging community. To illustrate the difficulty of generating a FAIR dataset and associated metadata upon publication, the FAIRness of the following open dataset was investigated (<https://bmcbiol.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12915-021-01072-7>). By using a tool developed by the Australian research data commons, it is possible to assess the FAIRness of a dataset (<https://ardc.edu.au/resources/aboutdata/fair-data/fair-self-assessment-tool/>). This tool demonstrates that the said dataset possesses a limited interoperability (i.e. no machine-readable data scheme). In addition, it was not possible to assess if the metadata would be available on the long-term. To conclude, local gaps in RDM literacy and FAIRification are still present within the bioimaging community in Flanders but tools are available to improve them.

To increase the visibility of the work, raw data of bioimage studies should be preferentially deposited in a dedicated repository such as bioimage archive rather than Figshare. Nevertheless, data deposition is more time-consuming in bioimage archive than in Figshare. Due to the large amount of data, the selection of the starting point to apply RDM is challenging. Hence, data management is a common effort with users and best practices should be defined within consortia. In addition, best practices should be tested by end users at different levels. Training initiatives are emerging at universities and various organizations such as Elixir Belgium.

Datahub: data management platform by R. Buono

ELIXIR Belgium offers different services related to data management throughout the data-life cycle: RDMkit, RDM Guide, DataHub, Galaxy, ENA, and WorkflowHub (<https://www.elixir-belgium.org/services>). Among those services, DataHub is a platform that aims at a FAIR by design approach for research data management (<https://datahub.elixir-belgium.org/>). DataHub is based on the open-source software FAIRDOME-SEEK. DataHub makes use of the ISA framework (ISA: Investigation, Study, Assay), which is somewhat harmonious with the REMBI guidelines that FBI/BioImage Archive is applying. The ISA-compliant metadata description can be packaged as ISA-JSON files, a machine actionable format for metadata exchange. Future developments aim at using ISA-JSON files for submission to data repositories. These include the packaging of data and relevant metadata using the RO-Crate method (<https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>). DataHub enables to create different templates for sample types and for the specific repository (ENA, ArrayExpress...) and to manage the different permissions to the different parts of ISA, assets and templates. Within DataHub, attributes can be defined by controlled vocabulary from an ontology or link to a persistent identifier (PID). In addition, DataHub allows for validation of metadata and provides a search box for input values. In the future, DataHub aims for integration with Galaxy and WorkflowHub.

Nowadays, DataHub focuses on the data management for multi-omics but imaging data could also be integrated in the future.

Metadata & repositories in bioimaging by T. Woller

Within the FBI consortium, the active and archive data is stored in drives, commercial clouds or in public repositories (Biostudies) depending on the affiliation.

Workflow and codes are usually shared using Git platforms after publication or upon request. The handling of the metadata itself is problematic due to the lack of common ontologies within the bioimaging community. Therefore, developing guidelines, training and user-friendly software are required. The standard "recommended metadata for bioimaging" REMBI was developed during an international workshop focusing on bioimages (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41592-021-01166-8>). REMBI considers relevant metadata associated to biological images and has been implemented as a standard for biological images at the bioimage archive. FBI started a pilot project on data management of bioimages using REMBI as an ontology and iRODS as data management system in collaboration with VSC. Metadata were saved as JSON files instead of CSV files due to the larger versatility and scalability of the JSON files over CSV files. The software tool micro-meta was also tested to extract the metadata from the image acquisition of the microscope. However, handling JSON files is challenging for users while, the software tool micro-meta is tedious to extract the technical data from complex microscopes.

An alternative would be to extract the data from the image acquisition from the microscope itself with a script. In addition, the standard REMBI contains redundant information and is missing other relevant information. Regarding FAIR data, users desire well-documented guidelines/examples and efficient workflow to extract metadata. The main challenges for open data reside in the time/resource investment coupled to the amount of data itself. To conclude, the number of fields in REMBI should be reduced, while the extraction of metadata should be facilitated by efficient workflows.

A conversion tool between CSV and JSON files would help to lower the barrier to use JSON files. However, filling up a spreadsheet is already a challenge, uncontrolled entries require curation on the longer term. So far, the REMBI template consists only of open fields due to the different types of datasets. However, various examples are provided in the annex of the paper presenting REMBI. On the one hand, ISA is a model, and the information can be a set of free attributes as a function of the requirements of the repositories (<https://isa-tools.org/>). On the other hand, REMBI is still an intermediate status between checklist and model. So, the scope of REMBI should be clarified, namely how much specificity will be allowed within REMBI. A good start would be to define broad metadata standards and some groups would require some additional specification/extension (i.e. additional fields). Metadata with technical fields should be extracted automatically/machine

actionable. Automation of the metadata is a crucial step, and a GUI would be useful. Metadata files are provided by commercial software but the format is not uniform and it is not standardized enough. The open microscopy consortium (OME) tries to harmonize the standards and it might be interesting to build up on those initiatives. The file organization is also very important and should be harmonized. Part of the problem comes from the repositories because the check-lists are different. The Micrometa app is more suited to simple microscopes but is ill-suited to build simple microscopes with multiband filters. In addition, it is important to define the end destination of the data, more specifically in which repository the data will be stored or archived (i.e. Bio image archive, university repository).

Discussion

As reproducible analysis is becoming a requirement for science, does REMBI enable reproducible analysis? A section on analysis is included in REMBI but it is not very elaborated. Hence, only use cases will demonstrate if this is currently enough. Currently, analysis tools are often shared via GitHub at the Lab Cell Biology & Histology (UAntwerpen) to allow open analysis. In addition, popular bioimage analysis software such as QuPath or Fiji enable recording macros that can be used posteriorly. Workflows and pipelines can be registered in WorkflowHub, described according to Common Workflow Language and linked to GitHub. WorkflowHub offers DOI and the link can be placed in the paper and datasets. Another player in the field of reproducible analysis are the Galaxy servers developed and maintained by ELIXIR ([useGalaxy.eu](https://usegalaxy.eu)). More specifically, Galaxy is suitable for standardized, consolidated, repetitive workflows that needs to be done repeatedly. Galaxy saves many parameters and steps that are adjusted during the workflow. Moreover, it provides some computing resources.

OMERO is a platform that is commonly used within the bioimaging community and that is planning to provide RDM by starting a collaboration with iRODS. In addition, OMERO possesses integrated plugins for image analysis. Within FBI, OMERO was installed in the past but abandoned because alternative services were faster and it had many issues (unsupported file formats, a lot of manual steps).

In general, images are stored by individual users in the long term and 5 years on the servers. Users need metadata associated to their data because they will store files long term (locally). High level metadata (project etc) are useful to make reports within core facilities. At VIB, core facilities act as enablers since many running projects are using the core facilities. Therefore, users should deposit the metadata at the creation of datasets.

At KU Leuven, users collect their data on the local hard drive because the access to L drive is quite cheap. To generalize the use of metadata, the metadata collection should be a very low threshold process. Automatic extraction of technical metadata and electronic lab notebook documentation could help to do so. In addition, a data management plan and experimental planning should become one of the first steps of a project. Nevertheless, a cultural shift is taking place, especially at undergraduate level where data management planning is taught during the curriculum.

Conclusion

Despite many challenges for data management in the field of bioimaging, numerous initiatives are emerging to facilitate the life of researchers in the field. The main issue will be to find an equilibrium between not reinventing the wheel and finding a system that will be adopted by most of the community. The international context of research and the scale of the task must motivate us to collaborate. Therefore, the communication between stakeholders is of utmost importance and we should remain in contact through workshops like this one.

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